

Ranking Based Beam Training for XLRIS

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Abstract—Extremely large-scale reconfigurable intelligent surface (XLRIS) is pivotal for 6G millimeter wave and terahertz networks, enhancing performance and coverage by creating alternative links between the base station and the user equipment (UE). However, their passive nature and near-field (NF) propagation characteristics resulting from large XLRIS aperture size make passive beamforming (PBF) a complex process. Traditional beam training (BT) methods, e.g., exhaustive search (EX) based NF codebooks (NFCB), incurs high overhead and complexity. Multi-stages approaches risk outage and misalignment, meanwhile position-based codebooks require frequent and complex redesigns in multi-user or mobile scenarios, limiting their practicality. To overcome these challenges, this paper proposes a novel ranking-based beam training (RBT) approach. By leveraging available UE position information, the RBT scheme intelligently ranks all codewords in the conventional NFCB based on their similarity to the UE's location. Then, instead of a long EX, the system only tests the top N_c ranked candidates' beams, dramatically reducing training space and required power for BT. Numerical results demonstrate the practicality and the efficiency of the RBT which obtains close performance to the optimal EX based NFCB approach with significant reduction in the overhead.

Index Terms—Extremely large-scale RIS, near-field communication, beam training, ranking-based BT, 6G networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

6G networks are rapidly progressing depending on the promising technology of reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS) [1], [2]. More, specifically, the extremely large-scale version of RISs, which is called XLRIS [1], [3], is widely employed as electromagnetic wave reflecting surface in outdoor and urban scenarios, where it is deployed in buildings fronts. These XLRIS consists of massive number of adjustable passive elements to preserve energy consumption. By configuring the XLRIS elements' amplitude and phase, in what is called passive beamforming (PBF) [2], [4], the incident signal on XLRIS can be redirected to another direction, where targeted user equipments (UEs) exist. This characteristic is utilized to provide alternative line of sight (LOS) link when the main LOS path between the base station (BS) and the UE is blocked due to different type of obstacles, i.e., when blockage phenomenon occurs [1], [2], [5]. Moreover, it serves as a helpful link, if

the main LOS link exists. Employing XLRIS significantly improves system performance such as data rate, coverage, readability and energy efficiency particularly in challenging environments in 6G networks [1], [4].

However, due to XLRIS passive nature, the PBF task is highly complicated as the elements cannot be used for exchanging control signal, hence the BS-XLRIS and XLRIS-UE channels cannot directly be estimated [1]. Moreover, with massive number of XLRISs elements, estimating the full channels needs long delay, high complexity and overhead. Utilizing codebooks (CBs) based PBF approaches have been recently adopted to relax complexity and reduce overhead, and simultaneously overcome the limitation of estimating the full channel [2], [4]. Nevertheless, XLRIS has a special structure which makes the physical aperture grows and increases the Rayleigh distance. Hence, the electromagnetic wave propagates in the near-field (NF) region making far-field based CBs inefficient for passive beamforming [3].

The authors in [3] proposed conventional near-field codebook (NFCB) then suggested exhaustive search (EX) for beam training (BT) for XLRIS. But, due to high overhead and complexity, they further developed NF based hierarchical based codebook (NFHCB) approach for PBF, where BT is done in two phases. In [6], the authors proposed NF rainbow based BT approach benefiting from the spatial features in wideband signals. The authors in [7], [8], [9], [10] developed different two-phases hierarchical and multi-BT schemes to relax full traditional NFCB complexity. Though lower overhead and delay reduction, HCB and multi-stages based approaches suffer outage and misalignment issues, mainly if the first stage fails to detect a promising codeword and sequentially the following stages will be ineffective, also they still requires high overhead. The authors in [11] proposed positioning based CB (PCB) for XLRIS PBF. However, this PCB needs to be frequently reconstructed to handle mobility and multiuser scenarios. Moreover, the system shall redesign this PCB at each new frame based on associated UEs positions. Hence, this PCB needs additional system complexity even if the PCB size is small which makes PCB [11] in inefficient solution.

In this paper, to existing BT schemes' limitations, we propose a ranking based beam training (RBT) approach to

Fig. 1: XLRIS aided downlink communication systems.

significantly reduce the beam training overhead by leveraging user equipment (UE) position information. In RBT approach, instead of exhaustively testing all possible NFCB codewords, the system first retrieves the UE's position, then calculates distances' vector between this UE position and the pre-stored positions associated with each beam codeword in the conventional codebook. The algorithm ranks all codewords based on these calculated distances and shrinks the searching space to only top N_c promising candidates beams to identify the best beam for transmission. The RBT reaches near optimal achievable rate performance with lower overhead than other BT solutions, where RBT needs only N_c beams for BT. Hence, the RBT scheme is a practical solution for reducing BT time and power consumption without compromising performance.

The paper is organized as: Section II and III presents system and channel model, and NFCB design and training steps. The proposed RBT is demonstrated in Section IV. Section V and VI present the numerical results and conclusion of the paper.

II. SYSTEM AND CHANNEL MODEL

In this work, as shown in Figure 1, we consider an XLRIS aided downlink system where a fixed base station (BS) equipped with M antennas serves a single-antenna UE via the assistant of XLRIS, as the direct BS-UE link is fully blocked. The XLRIS is a planar surface consist of $N = N_x \times N_y$ passive elements and is centered at the origin.

Let $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ and $\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times N}$ denote the BS-XLRIS and XLRIS-UE channels, respectively. The XLRIS is a diagonal RIS, hence the XLRIS phase shift matrix $\Theta = \text{diag}(\theta)$, where $\theta = [\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_N]^T$ is the XLRIS PBF vector and $\theta_n = \gamma_n e^{j\phi_n}$, here the n th element amplitude is $\gamma_n \in [0, 1]$ and phase is $\phi_n \in [0, 2\pi)$. The BS active beamforming vector is $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ and the transmitted symbol to the UE is s . Thus, the received signal at the UE can be presented as

$$r = \mathbf{h} \Theta \mathbf{G} \mathbf{v} s + z_n, \quad (1)$$

where $z_n \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma^2)$ is complex Gaussian noise. As a result of fixed BS and XLRIS locations, active beamforming, i.e., configuring \mathbf{v} , is assumed to be done [2], [4]. Hence, the focus is conducting the PBF training process to align the reflected XLRIS beam with the main path between the XLRIS and UE.

A. Near-Field Channel Model

The Rayleigh distance in RIS-aided systems is $Z = \frac{2D_{RIS}^2}{\lambda}$, where D_{RIS} refers to the RIS aperture and λ denotes the signal

wavelength. The XLRIS has a large aperture D_{RIS} enlarging the Rayleigh distance and makes the reflected signal by XLRIS pointing to the near-field region instead of far-field region [3], [12]. Hence, the spherical wave model shall be adopted.

The n th XLRIS element coordinate is $(x_{n_x}, y_{n_y}, 0)$, where $x_{n_x} = \left(n_x - \frac{N_x+1}{2}\right)d_R$ and $y_{n_y} = \left(n_y - \frac{N_y+1}{2}\right)d_R$, where d_R is elements spacing, $n_x = 1, \dots, N_x$ and $n_y = 1, \dots, N_y$. Noting that all coordinates are normalized by the wavelength.

Let (x_r, y_r, z_r) denotes the coordinate corresponding to the main XLRIS-UE path scatter, hence the XLRIS-UE channel in the near-field can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{h}_{NF}^r = \alpha_r \mathbf{c}^T(x_r, y_r, z_r), \quad (2)$$

where α_r is the XLRIS-UE path gain and $\mathbf{c}(x_r, y_r, z_r)$ is the array steering vector which presented as

$$\mathbf{c}(x_r, y_r, z_r) = \left[e^{-j2\pi D_r(1,1)}, \dots, e^{-j2\pi D_r(N_x, N_y)} \right]^T, \quad (3)$$

in which $D_r(n_x, n_y) = \sqrt{(x_r - x_{n_x})^2 + (y_r - y_{n_y})^2 + z_r^2}$.

Similarly, let (x_G, y_G, z_G) denotes the coordinate corresponding to the main BS-XLRIS path scatter, hence the BS-XLRIS channel in the NF can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{h}_{NF}^G = \alpha_G \mathbf{c}^T(x_G, y_G, z_G), \quad (4)$$

where α_G is the BS-XLRIS path gain, meanwhile the array steering vector $\mathbf{c}(x_G, y_G, z_G) = \left[e^{-j2\pi D_G(1,1)}, \dots, e^{-j2\pi D_G(N_x, N_y)} \right]^T$, where $D_G(n_x, n_y) = \sqrt{(x_G - x_{n_x})^2 + (y_G - y_{n_y})^2 + z_G^2}$. Hence, the effective cascaded BS-XLRIS-UE channel can be expressed as

$$\bar{\mathbf{h}}_{NF} = \alpha_r \alpha_G \bar{\mathbf{c}}((x_G, y_G, z_G), (x_r, y_r, z_r)), \quad (5)$$

where

$$\bar{\mathbf{c}}((x_G, y_G, z_G), (x_r, y_r, z_r)) = \left[e^{-j2\pi D(1,1)}, \dots, e^{-j2\pi D(1, N_y)}, \dots, e^{-j2\pi D(N_x, 1)}, \dots, e^{-j2\pi D(N_x, N_y)} \right]^T, \quad (6)$$

in which $D(n_x, n_y) = D_G(n_x, n_y) + D_r(n_x, n_y)$. Note that the selected optimal beam, if EX is employed for NFCB, depends on the scatters corresponding to the UE. Hence, imagine that the UE exact position is known, i.e., the scattering point (x_r, y_r, z_r) is known, hence the BT process will not be needed, however that cannot be obtained.

III. CONVENTIONAL NFCB DESIGN AND BEAM TRAINING

In this section, we briefly present the NFCB design steps and beam training method that are proposed in [3], as this traditional CB is the base for our proposed RBT approach.

In the conventional NFCB for XLRIS, the entire considered three-dimensional (3D) space, i.e., the environment space covered by the XLRIS, is divided into several sampled points in the x - y - z coordinate system considering sampling step Δ . The NF cascaded array steering vector $\bar{\mathbf{c}}$ of the NF cascaded channel $\bar{\mathbf{h}}_{NF}$ is determined by the sum of the distance from (x_G, y_G, z_G) to the XLRIS and the distance from (x_r, y_r, z_r)

to the XLRIS, hence each codeword for XLRIS is related to these pair of sampled points in the x - y - z coordinate system.

Let \mathcal{P}_r refers to the collection of the sampled points corresponding to (x_r, y_r, z_r) , and can be presented as

$$\mathcal{P}_r = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} x_s^r = X_{\min}^r, X_{\min}^r + \Delta x^r, \dots, X_{\max}^r; \\ y_s^r = Y_{\min}^r, Y_{\min}^r + \Delta y^r, \dots, Y_{\max}^r; \\ z_s^r = Z_{\min}^r, Z_{\min}^r + \Delta z^r, \dots, Z_{\max}^r \end{array} \right\} \quad (7)$$

where Δx^r , Δy^r , and Δz^r are the NFCB sampling step on the x -, y -, and z -axes for \mathcal{P}_r , respectively. Using any sampled point (x_s^r, y_s^r, z_s^r) alongside BS scattering point (x_G, y_G, z_G) , the effective sampled distance between the two scattering points $D_s(n_x, n_y)$ is expressed similar to $D(n_x, n_y)$. Using $D_s(n_x, n_y)$, the sampled steering vector $\bar{\mathbf{c}}_s$ is computed as in (6), then the NFCB \mathbf{F} is constructed as $\mathbf{F} = [\mathbf{F}, \bar{\mathbf{c}}_s]$ after passing through all possible scattering combinations without repetition. The work in [3] discussed NFCB design in details.

For BT, the system search along all \mathbf{F} codewords, then receiving feedback from UE indicating the received signal strength obtained from each codeword, thereafter it selects the optimal beam achieving the the highest signal strength. The NFCB contains F codewords, where each f codeword has corresponding positioning record for the sampled point $\mathbf{p}[f] = (x_s^r, y_s^r, z_s^r)$, that are used for constructing this codeword. The NFCB is large as the sampling points are huge due to the network coverage, causing high searching overhead and long delay. Thus, to reduce this, we propose a lower overhead ranking based beam training approach in the next section.

IV. PROPOSED RANKING BASED BT APPROACH

In the proposed RBT, the system ranks the NFCB codewords corresponding to the targeted UE position to determine the best beam for serving a certain UE by . To do so, the system retrieve the UE position $\mathbf{u} = (x_u, y_u, z_u)$. Then, it computes the metric or similarity based distances vector $\mathbf{d} = [d[1], d[2], \dots, d[F]]$ between the UE position vector \mathbf{u} and the vector of each codeword positioning record, i.e., $\mathbf{p}[f], \forall f \in F$, that are used for building the NFCB considering $\Delta = 10$. Note that the UE position is obtained using available Wi-Fi signal, which has accuracy error of 2.5 m [13]. Thereafter, the system ranks the codewords based on their calculated distances and searches only on the first N_c codewords to determine the best codeword to be used for the UE in the transmission period. N_c , which is the number of searching beams in RBT approach, is a design parameter that depends on the trade-off between the required performance and acceptable overhead. As we will show in the numerical result section, N_c is small comparable to NFCB size, which highly reduces the training overhead.

Several metric or similarity distances are used to rank the NFCB codewords, in this work, we use Euclidean, Cosine, Correlation, Hamming, and Chebyshev distances, then, we study the RBT performance when using each distance. In the following, we present the equations used for computing $d[f]$ using each distance. The metric distances, i.e, Euclidean

Algorithm 1 Proposed Ranking based Beam Training

- 1: **Input:** $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{p}[f], \forall f \in F$, and N_c .
 - 2: **Output:** Selected best codeword f^*
 - 3: **Initialize** distance vector $\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{0}$.
 - 4: **for** $f = 1 \rightarrow F$ **do**
 - 5: **Compute** the distance $d[f](\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{p}[f])$ according to the utilized distance using (8), (9), (10), (11) or (12).
 - 6: **Append** $d[f]$ to \mathbf{d} .
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: **Rank** F codewords according to ascending order of $d[f]$.
 - 9: **Select** top N_c codewords for candidate search.
 - 10: **Search** the N_c candidates to find out the best codeword f^* that achieves the highest received power.
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distance $d_{\text{Euc}}[f]$, Hamming distance $d_{\text{Ham}}[f]$ and Chebyshev distance $d_{\text{Chev}}[f]$ can be expressed, respectively, as

$$d_{\text{Euc}}[f](\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{p}[f]) = \sqrt{(x_u - x_s^r)^2 + (y_u - y_s^r)^2 + (z_u - z_s^r)^2}, \quad (8)$$

$$d_{\text{Ham}}[f](\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{p}[f]) = \frac{1}{3} \left(\mathbf{1}_{\{x_u \neq x_s^r\}} + \mathbf{1}_{\{y_u \neq y_s^r\}} + \mathbf{1}_{\{z_u \neq z_s^r\}} \right), \quad (9)$$

$$d_{\text{Chev}}[f](\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{p}[f]) = \max \left\{ |x_u - x_s^r|, |y_u - y_s^r|, |z_u - z_s^r| \right\}. \quad (10)$$

The similarity distances, i.e., Cosine distance $d_{\text{Cos}}[f]$ and Correlation distance $d_{\text{Corr}}[f]$ are expressed, respectively, as

$$d_{\text{Cos}}[f](\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{p}[f]) = 1 - \frac{x_u x_s^r + y_u y_s^r + z_u z_s^r}{\sqrt{x_u^2 + y_u^2 + z_u^2} \sqrt{(x_s^r)^2 + (y_s^r)^2 + (z_s^r)^2}}, \quad (11)$$

$$d_{\text{Corr}}[f](\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{p}[f]) = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^3 (u_i - \bar{u})(p_i - \bar{p})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^3 (u_i - \bar{u})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^3 (p_i - \bar{p})^2}}. \quad (12)$$

where \bar{u} and \bar{p} are the means of \mathbf{u} and $\mathbf{p}[f]$, respectively. Algorithm 1 summarizes the proposed RBT approach steps. The computational complexity of the proposed algorithm is mainly dominated by computing distances which requires $O(3F)$ time and ranking the F distances that needs $O(F \log F)$ time. The search among the top N_c candidates adds $O(N_c)$ considering constant-time for received power evaluation. Therefore, the overall complexity is $O(3F + F \log F + N_c)$, with an additional memory cost of $O(F)$ for storing the distance vector. The computational complexity and memory storage are law comparable to the benefits obtained by employing the proposed RBT scheme as we will further clarify.

V. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, we provide numerical results to present the proposed RBT approach performance comparable to the conventional NFCB beam training and the optimal channel state information (CSI) based beamforming schemes, though it is impractical to be applied due to XLRIS size.

In the simulations, system parameters are $M = 64$ and $N = N_x \times N_y = 128 \times 4 = 512$. The path gains are modeled as $\alpha_G \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ and $\alpha_r \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$. The adjacent XLRIS elements space $d_R = 1/2$ [12]. The BS is fixed at $(-50, 0, -10)$ and XLRIS is at $(0, 0, 0)$ in x - y - z coordinates system,

Fig. 2: (a) Achievable rates against different number of candidate beams when SNR = 5 dB and $\Delta = 10$, (b) achievable rate versus SNR considering $N_c = 10$, and (c) beam training overhead versus sampling step Δ .

meanwhile the UE is assumed to be located within a 3D region bounded by $[0, 200]$, $[-25, 25]$, and $[-25, -5]$. $s = 1$ and $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{f}^*/M$, thus, the effective transmitted symbol becomes $\bar{s} = 1$. The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is defined as $1/\sigma^2$.

Figure 2a presents the achievable rate of RBT approaches versus number of candidate beams and comparable to benchmark CSI, NFCB and NFHCB based approaches, considering SNR = 5dB and $\Delta = 10$. Figure 2a shows that the proposed RBT approach, considering Euclidean, Manhattan and Chebyshev distances, can obtain nearly the same achievable rate as the traditional NFCB based approach with much less number of candidate beams, N_c almost 20, where Euclidean based RBT approach is leading other distances based RBT schemes. Moreover, it needs only 10 candidate beams to overcome the NFHCB based scheme achievable rate. Noting that similarity based RBT approaches require higher overhead to approach the same performance as distances based RBT schemes.

In the following, we consider the RBT approaches with $N_c = 10$. Figure 2b presents the achievable rate of the proposed RBT approaches comparable to CSI, NFCB and NFHCB based approaches considering different SNR values. It is clear that Euclidean based RBT approach is leading over other RBT schemes and NFHCB based scheme and its performance is close to conventional NFCB based approach. Finally, Figure 2c discusses the training overhead in terms of the number of searching beams for the proposed RBT approaches comparable to NFCB and NFHCB based approaches versus sampling steps. The proposed RBT approach requires only 10 candidate beams, which is nearly 4% of the overhead required for NFCB in case of $\Delta = 10$, and is less than the required beams for other approaches even if lower sampling step is considered. For example, the number of searching beams for the NFCB based approach with $\Delta = 25$ is 10-times of the required RBT candidate beams.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper has introduced a novel ranking-based beam training (RBT) approach that effectively addresses the critical challenge of BT overhead in XLRIS systems. By leveraging user position information to intelligently rank and select candidate beams, our method significantly reduces the searching

overhead associated with conventional NFCB based approach. Numerical results demonstrate that metric based RBT approaches leading by Euclidean based RBT approach achieves performance close to NFCB based scheme while requiring only 10 candidate beams for training. The proposed framework maintains robust performance across varying SNR conditions and sampling steps. Considering artificial intelligence for RBT can be future extension of this work, where such approach can be helpful for dynamic environments and mobile scenarios.

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